

On the Gain Available From a Passive Synthetic Aperture Array

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Abstract - Passive synthetic aperture processing intrinsically involves a trade-off between temporal and spatial gain. This is because the time available for the temporal processing of each element is reduced in proportion to the number of virtual sensors created. However, when the noise field is non-isotropic, the generation of a synthetic aperture can, in many circumstances, result in a large increase in total gain over that of the physical array from which the synthetic aperture was generated. Several examples are presented based on a simple non-isotropic noise field, that illustrate this phenomenon.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent studies have demonstrated the feasibility of passive synthetic aperture processing for acoustic towed arrays [1-7]. The main advantage of synthetic aperture processing is the creation of an acoustic aperture larger than that provided by the original physical aperture. This improvement in array gain is achieved at the cost of temporal gain however, since synthetic aperture algorithms use the physical hydrophones a multiplicity of times in order to create virtual hydrophones, thus reducing the processing time available for the totality of hydrophones in the synthetic array. For example, if one has a maximum of $T = M\Delta t$ seconds available to process a sinusoidal acoustic signal, where M is the number of independent samples and Δt is the (Nyquist) sample time, the available signal to noise ratio at a single hydrophone in the time domain is given by

$$SNR = \frac{P_s}{\sigma^2} M = P_s/\eta \quad (1)$$

Here, $P_s = |A|^2/2$ where A is the (possibly complex) amplitude of the signal, $\eta = \sigma^2/M$ is the filtered noise and σ^2 is the variance (power) of the noise, which is assumed to be white. Since P_s/σ^2 is the input signal to noise ratio at the single hydrophone, it follows that the temporal gain, G_t , is equal to M , the number of independent time

samples. Following an argument put forth by Autrey and others [8], if one uses a single hydrophone to construct a passive synthetic aperture of N hydrophones in white, spatially isotropic noise, since the processing time is constrained to T seconds, there are now only M/N time samples available for processing each of the synthetic hydrophones. Hence, the temporal gain at each (synthetic) hydrophone is

$$G'_t = G_t/N \quad (2)$$

Assuming uncorrelated noise between each of the synthetic hydrophones, the array gain available from the synthetic aperture array is $AG = N$, so that the total gain available is

$$G_{total} = G'_t AG = G'_t N = G_t \quad (3)$$

That is, there is no new gain.

In Reference 8 it is concluded on the basis of this argument that passive synthetic aperture arrays serve no useful purpose. This argument is valid if one is working in an isotropic noise field and is concerned only with total gain and not directionality. In a more general sense however, this conclusion is not true, since what has been achieved by the synthetic aperture algorithm is the ability to convert temporal gain to array gain. Thus one can achieve directionality (array gain) at the expense of temporal gain, and what is more important, in the case of non-isotropic noise fields, the increased array gain from the passive synthetic aperture can provide an enormous improvement. As an example, consider the case of a towed array in a noise field that contains an interfering signal that is displaced from the target by an angle that is smaller than the half beamwidth of the physical array. In this case we will show that the formation of a synthetic aperture that is able to resolve the interference from the target is capable of providing a very large increase in the gain available to the system. This is a particularly interesting case, since it is a realistic situation and, at the

same time, lends itself to a simple analysis. Intuitively, it is not difficult to see what is happening. First, the interference is a source of particularly troublesome noise, since it originates from a highly localized point in space and therefore its field is highly correlated. Second, since the synthetic aperture array can provide a situation in which the interference is in or very near to a zero in the beam pattern, the interference can be very effectively notched out, providing a large increase in spatial gain at the expense of a much smaller loss in temporal gain. A third point to be made here is that, since a non-isotropic noise field can be thought of as a combination of an isotropic component and one or more directional components, the directional components can be thought of as sources that are quite localized in space and therefore cause spatial correlations in the noise field. The example that we provide here is simply a special case of such a situation. Thus, any synthetic aperture scheme that can act against such localized sources is providing gain against components of the noise field that are correlated. Clearly, this is a great advantage.

II. ARRAY GAIN

The plane wave array factor for an N -element receiving array is given by [9]

$$p(\theta, \theta_o, \phi, \phi_o) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N a_n e^{i r_n \cdot (k - k_o)} \quad (4)$$

where a_n is the (generally complex) weighting coefficient for the n th element, r_n is the position vector of the n th element of the array, k is the wave vector of a narrow band plane wave signal with direction (θ, ϕ) , and k_o is the wave vector in the steering direction (θ_o, ϕ_o) . Both k and k_o have magnitude $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ where λ is the wavelength. For the case of a line array on the z -axis with point elements spaced by a distance d , equation (4) reduces to

$$p(\theta, \theta_o) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N a_n e^{i k n d (\sin \theta - \sin \theta_o)}. \quad (5)$$

The polar coordinate system we use here is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Definition of the spherical coordinate system used in this study.

The receive directivity function is defined by

$$b(\theta, \theta_o) = |p(\theta, \theta_o)|^2 = \frac{1}{N^2} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N a_n a_m^* e^{i k d_{n,m} (\sin \theta - \sin \theta_o)}. \quad (6)$$

Here, $d_{n,m} = d(n - m)$ and for purposes of normalization, we assume $\sum_{n=1}^N a_n = N$. This is the plane wave power pattern for a receiving line array of N point elements that is steered in the θ_o direction.

If the directional intensity function of the noise field is represented by $\Gamma(\theta, \phi)$, the noise received at a single element is

$$\eta = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \Gamma(\theta, \phi) \cos \theta d\theta d\phi. \quad (7)$$

If $\Gamma(\theta, \phi)$ is a constant, then it is easy to show that

$$\Gamma = \frac{\eta}{4\pi}. \quad (8)$$

In this case the noise output of the N element array is given by

$$P_n(\theta_o) = \frac{1}{2} \eta \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} b(\theta, \theta_o) \cos \theta d\theta \quad (9)$$

where $b(\theta, \theta_o)$ is defined by equation (6). Thus, for a plane wave signal arriving at some angle θ' with power P_s , the output signal to noise ratio of the array is

$$(SNR)_{out} = \frac{P_s b(\theta')}{\frac{1}{2} \eta \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} b(\theta) \cos \theta d\theta}. \quad (10)$$

In equation (10) and that which follows, the dependence on θ_o is suppressed for simplicity.

Upon integrating the denominator of equation (10), setting $\theta' = \theta_0$ and assuming unity shading (which we will assume for the remainder of this paper), we have

$$(SNR)_{out} = \frac{P_s}{\eta \frac{1}{N^2} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N \frac{\sin(kd_{n,m})}{kd_{n,m}} e^{-ikd_{n,m} \sin \theta_0}} \quad (11)$$

or

$$(SNR)_{out} = (SNR)_{in} AG \quad (12)$$

where $(SNR)_{in} = P_s/\eta$ and AG is the *array gain* for the case of a plane wave arriving at angle θ_0 on a line array in an isotropic noise field. Here, $(SNR)_{in}$ is meant to denote the *SNR* into the array. It is, in fact, the *output SNR* of the temporal processor for each element of the physical array. For this case (plane wave in an isotropic noise field), $10 \log_{10}(AG)$ is defined as the *directivity index (DI)* of the array. Note that when the element spacing d is equal to $\lambda/2$, the noise is completely uncorrelated. Hence, the double summation in the denominator of equation (11) becomes equal to N , so that the array gain for the case at hand (isotropic noise field), becomes

$$AG = N. \quad (13)$$

Since this is the case for totally uncorrelated noise, the array gain for the case of an isotropic noise field can never exceed N .

III. NON-ISOTROPIC NOISE

Generally speaking, the output SNR of a line array for a plane wave signal with power P_s arriving at angle θ' is

$$(SNR)_{out} = \frac{P_s b(\theta')}{\int_0^{2\pi} \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} b(\theta) \Gamma(\theta, \phi) \cos \theta d\theta d\phi}. \quad (14)$$

In this case the array gain is given by

$$AG = \frac{b(\theta')}{\int_0^{2\pi} \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} b(\theta) \frac{\Gamma(\theta, \phi)}{\eta} \cos \theta d\theta d\phi} \quad (15)$$

where η is defined in equation (7). We now consider the case of a noise field consisting of an isotropic component and a narrow band plane wave source of interference at angle $\theta = \theta_j, \phi = 0$. Thus

$$\Gamma(\theta, \phi) = \frac{\eta'}{4\pi} + J\delta(\theta - \theta_j, 0) \quad (16)$$

where $\delta(\theta - \theta_j, 0)$ is the spherical delta function and is defined by $\delta(\theta - \theta', \phi - \phi') = 0$ unless $\theta = \theta', \phi = \phi'$ and

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} f(\theta, \phi) \delta(\theta - \theta', \phi - \phi') \cos \theta d\theta d\phi = f(\theta', \phi'). \quad (17)$$

for any integrable function $f(\theta, \phi)$. With the help of equation (7), it is easy to show that, for this case, the noise on a single hydrophone is $\eta' + J$ and the noise output of the full array is

$$\begin{aligned} P_{noise} &= \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \left[\frac{\eta'}{4\pi} + J\delta(\theta - \theta_j, 0) \right] b(\theta) \cos \theta d\theta d\phi \\ &= \frac{\eta'}{N} + Jb(\theta_j). \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

When the array is steered to the target, the signal power out of the array is given by

$$P_s b(\theta' = \theta_0) = P_s, \quad (19)$$

so that the output SNR is given by

$$(SNR)_{out} = \frac{P_s}{P_{noise}} = \frac{NP_s}{\eta' + NJb(\theta_j)}. \quad (20)$$

When $J = 0$, this reduces to $(SNR)_{out} = (SNR)_{in} N$, as expected. The appearance of the factor N multiplying the interference term is a consequence of it being correlated over the whole array, since it arises from a point source.

Since $(SNR)_{in} = P_s/(\eta' + J)$, equation (20) can be rewritten as

$$(SNR)_{out} = (SNR)_{in} AG \quad (21)$$

where

$$AG = \frac{N + r}{1 + rb(\theta_j)} \quad (22)$$

with $r = NJ/\eta'$, i.e., N times the "interference to noise" ratio.

Suppose we are now given T seconds for processing and we generate an N' element array from our N element array by using some synthetic aperture algorithm. The time available for temporal processing will be correspondingly reduced, since the physical hydrophones are being used to create virtual hydrophones. The degree of this reduction will depend upon the particular algorithm

used. There are two algorithms that have been experimentally verified. One is the "overlap-correlator" developed by Stergiopoulos and Sullivan [2], and the method developed by Yen and Carey [3]. Both of these algorithms use sequential measurements of the physical array which are then concatenated, with appropriate phase adjustments, to form a synthetic aperture. Thus, both methods are iterative. In the case of the overlap-correlator method, each iteration increases the length of the synthetic aperture by one half of the physical aperture, whereas in the case of the method of Yen and Carey, the synthetic aperture length is increased by a full physical aperture at each iteration.

Define $p = N'/N$ as the number of multiples of the physical aperture in the synthetic aperture and $q = T/\tau$ where τ is the time available for each iteration so that $q - 1$ is the number of iterations. It is easy to show that, in the case of the overlap correlator of Stergiopoulos and Sullivan, $p = (q + 1)/2$, and for the case of the Yen and Carey algorithm, $p = q$. Here, both p and q are assumed to be integers. Defining R as the ratio of the output SNR of the synthetic array to that of the physical array, we have, using equation (20),

$$R = \left(\frac{p}{q}\right) \frac{P_s N}{\eta' + N' J b'(\theta_j)} \div \frac{P_s N}{\eta' + N J b(\theta_j)}$$

$$= \frac{p}{q} \left\{ \frac{1 + r b(\theta_j)}{1 + p r b'(\theta_j)} \right\} \quad (23)$$

with $b'(\theta)$ being the power pattern of the synthetic array. Note that $R = p/q$ when $J = 0$. Thus in the case of the Yen and Carey algorithm, where $p/q = 1$, there is consistency with the conclusion of Reference 8 that in the case of isotropic noise fields, there is no new gain available. For the case of the overlap correlator method of Stergiopoulos and Sullivan, $p/q = (q + 1)/2q$, so that in this case, the total gain is reduced by about one half. Thus, in contradiction to the conclusion of reference 8, there is actually less total gain.

We now consider two special cases. First, suppose that the value of θ_j is such that it falls on a null of $b'(\theta)$ but not on a null of $b(\theta)$. Then

$$R = \frac{p}{q} (1 + r b(\theta_j)). \quad (24)$$

Figure 2. Plot of R , the gain ratio, as a function of r , the interference to noise ratio times N , for four values of the interference angle θ_j . The numbers 1,2,3,4 labeling the curves correspond to $\theta_j = .9^\circ, 1.8^\circ, 2.7^\circ$ and 3.6° , respectively. In all cases, the value of θ_j lies within the main lobe of the physical array. The first null of the synthetic array is approximately equal to 1.8°

Here, as expected, a great deal of improvement can be realized, especially in the case of a large value of J/η' , the interference to noise ratio. As a second example, consider the case where θ_j is not in a null of either $b'(\theta_j)$ or $b(\theta_j)$, and $r \gg 1$. Then

$$R \simeq \frac{1}{q} \frac{b(\theta_j)}{b'(\theta_j)}. \quad (25)$$

In this case, at any value of θ_j where $b/b' > q$, we realize an improvement.

Although these two rather simple examples are illuminating, it is of interest to look at the behavior of R from a more general point of view. In Figure 2 R is plotted as a function of r (the interference to noise ratio x N) for four values of θ_j , the arrival angle of the interference, for the case of a physical array with 32 elements spaced at $d = \lambda/2$, and a synthetic aperture array with 128 elements generated by the Yen and Carey method. Thus, $N = 32$, $N' = 128$, and $p = 4$. It is easy to show that the first null of $b'(\theta_j)$ occurs at $\theta_j = 2/N'$. Thus, we have selected

$\theta_j = 1/N', 2/N', 4/N'$ and $8/N'$ for the four cases shown in Figure 2. Since $N' = 128$, the first null of $b'(\theta_j)$ occurs at $2/N'$ radians which is equivalent to $.9^\circ$ degrees. The four values considered in Figure 2 correspond to one angle between the main response axis (MRA) of the synthetic pattern and the first null, one approximately at the first null, a third angle near the peak of the first sidelobe and a fourth angle near the second null. All four of these angles lie within the main lobe of the physical array pattern.

IV. DISCUSSION

The four values of θ_j considered in Figure 2 consist of two values that are near nulls of the synthetic aperture pattern function, whereas the other two are not. The smallest value of θ_j considered, $\theta_j = .9^\circ$, corresponds to an angle roughly half way between the MRA and the first null. For this case it can be seen from Figure 2 that the value of the gain ratio R is less than one. That is, the physical array is outperforming the synthetic array. This situation arises because the interference is inside the main lobe of both the synthetic and the physical array so that the synthetic array provides very little improvement in array gain, whereas there is a loss in temporal gain of a factor of four ($p = 4$). For the case of $\theta_j = 1.8^\circ$, the interference is very near the first null of the synthetic aperture while still well within the main lobe of the physical array. Hence, there is a great deal of improvement. In the case of $\theta_j = 2.7^\circ$, the interference is still within the main lobe of the physical array but near the peak of the first sidelobe of the synthetic array. In this case the synthetic aperture still outperforms the physical array due to the low level of the first sidelobe of the synthetic aperture pattern. The fourth case, $\theta_j = 3.6^\circ$, is a case where the interference angle is again still within the first null of the physical array but very close to the second null of the synthetic array so that the synthetic array again greatly outperforms the physical array. For values of θ_j approaching 7.2° , the behavior begins to become more complicated since the first null of the physical array beam pattern is being approached. Thus there will be a complicated interplay between the nulls of the two beam patterns, producing situations where the physical array will sometimes outperform the synthetic array and sometimes not.

It should be reiterated here that the results depicted in Figure 2 are based on the sequential Fourier transform method employed by Yen and Carey. If the overlap-correlator of Stergiopoulos and Sullivan were used instead,

the gains would be reduced by about 3 dB.

It is interesting to note that for the cases where the synthetic array outperforms the physical array, the improvement increases with r ; that is, increasing J/η' improves the situation. This is because the synthetic array is tending to notch out the interference where the physical array is not, so that increasing the value of J/η' will decrease the gain of the physical array very rapidly compared to the synthetic array, thereby increasing the value of R .

Since the synthetic aperture length is arbitrary, synthetic aperture processing provides the flexibility of creating a large class of beam patterns, thereby permitting the placement of pattern nulls in almost any desired position. This flexibility can provide a very useful adjunct to adaptive spatial processing. Of course, there is ultimately a limit to the size of the synthetic aperture that can be created since it is ultimately limited by the number of elements in the physical array and the signal to noise ratio [10].

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